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Background/Objectives: Giant cell arteritis (GCA) presents in people over 50, with headaches, ocular involvement and large vessel vasculitis. A 30-item GCA-specific patient reported outcome measure (GCA PRO) has been developed and validated. In this pilot, the GCA PRO was tested in a clinical setting to explore its feasibility and acceptability to patients and clinicians as a communication tool.

Methods: Patients seen in Rheumatology or Ophthalmology Departments in Bristol and Leeds completed the GCA PRO prior to their consultation. It referred to patients' health-related quality of life over the past 7 days. Clinicians were provided with a copy of patients' responses and a summary sheet highlighting overall scores which they referred to during the consultation. After the appointment, patients and clinicians completed short answer questionnaire (SAQ) plus free-text feedback for reporting on the experience of use of the GCA PRO within the consultation.

Results: The GCA PRO was piloted during 16 clinic appointments. 16 patients, mean age (SD) of 74.7 (7.0), 11 (68.8%) female, 7 (43.8%) active disease and 5 (31.3%) with ocular involvement took part. Seven clinicians participated, 5 Rheumatologists and 2 Ophthalmologists. Eighty seven percent of patients agreed that the GCA PRO had helped them to explain their condition; clinicians agreed that the GCA PRO had helped them to understand the patient's condition 88% of the time (Table 1). Clinicians noted that "It was easier for the patient to convey his anxiety and feelings towards the disease and treatment" and that the GCA PRO "indirectly helped via prompting discussion of patient's anxieties and worries", however they were more equivocal on its impact on decision making: "Management plan was informed by sympto, bloods and stage of illness". Patients commented that "It helped us to plan how to manage my GCA based on my answers" and that "The questions seemed relevant and it was helpful to me to be able to think about them before the appointment".

Conclusions: The GCA-PRO was found to be an acceptable tool for use in clinic by patients and clinicians, especially in ter of explaining and understanding the patient's condition.

Disclosures: Nil

Table 1. Patient and clinician feedback summary responses (n=16 appointments)

Question	Patients N (%)	Clinicians N (%)	Response
Helped explain/understand situation	5 (31%)	7 (44%)	Strongly agree
	9 (56%)	7 (44%)	Agree
	2 (13%)	1 (6%)	Neither agree/disagree
	0 (0)	1 (6%)	Disagree
Helped joint decisions	4 (25%)	1 (6%)	Strongly agree
	4 (25%)	7 (44%)	Agree
	7 (44%)	7 (44%)	Neither agree/disagree
	1 (6%)	1 (6%)	Disagree
Would be helpful to repeat over time	2 (13%)	3 (19%)	Strongly agree
	7 (44%)	12(75%)	Agree
	4 (25%)	1 (6%)	Neither agree/disagree
	0 (0)	0 (0)	Disagree
Improved communication	4 (25%)	4 (25%)	Strongly agree
	5 (31%)	7 (44%)	Agree
	5 (31%)	5 (31%)	Neither agree/disagree
	2 (13%)	0 (0)	Disagree